

Solubilities and Free Energies of Transfer for *p*-Nitro- and *p*-Chloro-benzoic Acids in Aqueous Mixtures of 2-Methoxyethanol and 1,2-Dimethoxyethane

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The solubilities of the *p*-nitro- and *p*-chloro-benzoic acids in 2-methoxyethanol (ME) + water and 1,2-dimethoxyethane (DME) + water mixtures at 25° have been measured. The thermodynamic dissociation constants of the acids have been determined from pH and solubility measurements. The free energies of transfer of *p*-nitro- and *p*-chloro-benzoate ions [$\Delta G_i^\circ(A^-)$] from water to mixed solvent systems have been evaluated from the corresponding ΔG_i° values of the acids and $\Delta G_i^\circ(H^+)$ values previously determined in all the solvent systems. The overall dissociation behaviour of these acids is found to be dictated by the specific solute-solvent interactions besides the relative solvent basicities.

SOLUBILITIES and dissociation of substituted-benzoic acids were reported earlier^{1,2} in aqueous mixtures of methanol and ethanol. In this paper we report our studies on solubilities and dissociation constants of *p*-nitro- and *p*-chloro-benzoic acids in a series of aqueous mixtures of 2-methoxyethanol (ME) and 1,2-dimethoxyethane (DME). Since the solvent effect involves $\Delta G_i^\circ(H^+)$, and $\Delta G_i^\circ(A^-)$ values have been found to be different between alcohols and studied solvent systems, it would be interesting to study the proton transfer processes in this particular class of solvent media. Thus a study of dissociation in these two solvent systems may be expected to reveal the specific molecular picture of solvation of the species involved in the ionisation equilibria.

Experimental

ME (G.R., E. Merck) was distilled twice and the middle fraction was utilised. DME (Fluka, Purum) was first shaken with FeSO₄ (AnalaR) for 1-2 h, decanted and then distilled; the distillate then refluxed for 12 h and distilled over metallic sodium. Other chemicals were of analytical grade. Double-distilled water from all-glass distilling sets was used for preparing the solutions.

p-Chlorobenzoic acid (Fluka, Puriss) and *p*-nitrobenzoic acid (G.R., E. Merck) were crystallised from ethanol-water mixtures. The purity of the samples was tested by melting point determination. The solubilities of *p*-nitro- and *p*-chloro-benzoic acids were determined with the help of a Campbell solubility apparatus³. The solutions were taken in stoppered bottles, and shaken in a mechanical shaker for 12 h at room temperature (27-35°). The bottles were then thermostated at 25±0.01° for 24 h with occasional shaking and then filtered by

inversion of the apparatus at the same temperature. The concentrations of the saturated solutions from each bottle were determined by titration with a standard (0.1-0.01 *N*) caustic soda solution using phenolphthalein as indicator. The operations were repeated until successive results were in agreement. Four sets of experiments were performed for each percentage of the solvent mixture. The solubilities of *p*-nitro- and *p*-chloro-benzoic acids in molarity are recorded in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. The solubilities in water are found to be 0.0025 and 0.0008 mol dm⁻³, respectively (Tables 1 and 3) which agree fairly well with the literature values^{3,4}.

pH of the saturated solutions of the acids for each percentage of the mixed solvents were measured using a ECIL pH-meter having an accuracy of ± 0.01 pH unit. Proper calibration of the glass-calomel electrode and appropriate corrections⁵ for the change of the solvent compositions were made. The measurements were made at 25±0.01°. The dielectric constants of the solvent mixtures were taken from the literature^{6,7}.

Results and Discussion

The thermodynamic dissociation constant for the reaction,

(A⁻ = substituted benzoate ion) can be written as

$$K_T = \frac{C_{H^+} \times C_{A^-}}{C_{HA}} \times \frac{f_{\pm}^2}{f_{HA}} = \frac{C_{H^+}}{[C]_T - C_{H^+}} \times f_{\pm}^2 \quad (2)$$

where, $[C]_T$ is total *p*-nitro- or *p*-chloro-benzoic acid concentration, and C_{H^+} the concentration of $[H^+]$ in the saturated experimental solutions determined pH-metrically. The mean molar activity coefficients of the ions at different concentrations in aqueous

TABLE 1—SOLUBILITY AND *pK* VALUES OF *p*-NITROBENZOIC ACID IN ME+ WATER AT 25°

ME wt%	$1/\epsilon \times 10^3$	<i>A</i>	Solubility mol dm ⁻³	$-\log f_{\pm}$	Corrected pH	<i>pK</i>	<i>pK_T</i>
00	1.27	0.509	0.0025 (0.002516) ^a	0.02	3.12	3.48	3.50
10	1.34	0.549	0.0028	0.03	3.13	3.57	3.60
20	1.43	0.606	0.0039	0.03	3.12	3.73	3.76
30	1.56	0.691	0.0119	0.04	3.06	4.16	4.20
40	1.74	0.813	0.0146	0.04	3.14	4.42	4.46
50	1.99	0.995	0.0259	0.05	3.24	4.88	4.93
60	2.37	1.293	0.0518	0.06	3.23	5.17	5.23
70	2.92	1.768	0.0930	0.08	3.33	5.63	5.71
80	3.77	2.593	0.1984	0.10	3.43	6.15	6.25
90	5.26	4.278	0.3739	0.12	3.72	7.01	7.13
100	5.91	5.087	0.4884	—	—	—	—

^aRef 2TABLE 2—SOLUBILITY AND *pK* VALUES OF *p*-NITROBENZOIC ACID IN DME+ WATER AT 25°

DME wt%	$1/\epsilon \times 10^3$	<i>A</i>	Solubility mol dm ⁻³	$-\log f_{\pm}$	Corrected pH	<i>pK</i>	<i>pK_T</i>
10	1.40	0.587	0.0031	0.03	3.15	3.68	3.71
20	1.56	0.691	0.0042	0.04	3.15	3.84	3.88
30	1.76	0.827	0.0123	0.05	3.12	4.30	4.35
40	2.01	1.009	0.0294	0.05	3.07	4.59	4.64
50	2.35	1.277	0.0379	0.06	3.19	4.95	5.01
60	2.79	1.652	0.1821	0.09	3.09	5.44	5.53
70	3.58	2.401	0.3900	0.12	3.15	5.82	5.94
80	4.79	3.714	0.653 ^a	0.15	3.37	6.56	6.71
90	7.42	7.160	0.7509	0.19	3.75	7.38	7.57
100	14.12	18.811	0.8824	—	—	—	—

TABLE 3—SOLUBILITY AND *pK* VALUES OF *p*-CHLOROBENZOIC ACID IN ME+ WATER AT 25°

Solvent wt%	$1/\epsilon \times 10^3$	<i>A</i>	Solubility mol dm ⁻³	$-\log f_{\pm}$	Corrected pH	<i>pK</i>	<i>pK_T</i>
00	1.27	0.509	0.0008 (0.000797) ^a	0.01	3.62	3.99	4.00
10	1.34	0.549	0.0013	0.01	3.78	4.61	4.62
20	1.43	0.606	0.0026	0.02	3.70	4.78	4.80
30	1.56	0.691	0.0056	0.02	3.67	5.07	5.09
40	1.74	0.813	0.0112	0.03	3.62	5.28	5.31
50	1.99	0.995	0.0162	0.03	3.75	5.71	5.74
60	2.37	1.293	0.0334	0.03	3.85	6.22	6.25
70	2.92	1.768	0.0535	0.04	3.87	6.47	6.51
80	3.77	2.593	0.1268	0.06	3.92	6.94	7.00
90	5.26	4.278	0.2589	0.07	4.13	7.67	7.74
100	5.91	5.087	0.4031	—	—	—	—

^aRef 4TABLE 4—SOLUBILITY AND *pK* VALUES OF *p*-CHLOROBENZOIC ACID IN DME+ WATER AT 25°

DME wt%	$1/\epsilon \times 10^3$	<i>A</i>	Solubility mol dm ⁻³	$-\log f_{\pm}$	Corrected pH	<i>pK</i>	<i>pK_T</i>
10	1.40	0.587	0.0015	0.01	3.82	4.77	4.78
20	1.56	0.691	0.0030	0.02	3.83	5.12	5.14
30	1.76	0.827	0.0071	0.02	3.72	5.28	5.30
40	2.01	1.009	0.0202	0.03	3.67	5.64	5.67
50	2.35	1.277	0.0484	0.04	3.65	5.98	6.02
60	2.79	1.652	0.0946	0.05	3.71	6.39	6.44
70	3.58	2.401	0.2631	0.06	3.74	6.90	6.96
80	4.79	3.714	0.5107	0.07	4.09	7.88	7.95
90	7.42	7.160	0.6318	0.09	4.37	8.54	8.63
100	14.12	18.811	1.0369	—	—	—	—

and mixed solvents have been determined using the Debye-Hückel limiting law,

$$-\log f_{\pm} = A \sqrt{\mu} \quad (3)$$

with appropriate A values in mixed solvents calculated from the dielectric constant values in the literature. The activity coefficients of neutral benzoic acid have been assumed to be unity in the saturated solutions of benzoic acid in the respective solvents. The ionic strengths of the solutions have been determined from C_{H^+} values based on equation (1). The dissociation constant values of both the acids determined by the solubility measurements in aqueous mixtures of ME and DME have been recorded in Tables 1-4.

The free energies of transfer for the dissociation of substituted benzoic acids have been calculated using equation (4),

$$\Delta G_t^{\circ}(1) = \Delta G_s^{\circ} - \Delta G_w^{\circ} = -2.303 RT [\log K_{T(s)} - \log K_{T(w)}] \quad (4)$$

The standard free energies of transfer of *p*-nitro- and *p*-chloro-benzoic acids from water to mixed solvents were calculated using the relation,

$$\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{HA}) = \Delta G_s^{\circ}(\text{HA}) - \Delta G_w^{\circ}(\text{HA}) = -2.303 RT \log \frac{C_s}{C_w} \times \frac{f_s(\text{HA})}{f_w(\text{HA})} \quad (5)$$

where, C_s and C_w are solubilities of the acid in water and respective solvents in molar scale. However, the validity of this relation depends on the assumption that the ratio of the activity coefficients of the neutral acid in the saturated solutions in the mixed solvent and in water is unity⁸.

The free energy change accompanying the transfer of benzoate ion from the standard state in water to that in mixed solvent has been calculated using equation (7),

$$\Delta G_t^{\circ}(1) = \Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{H}^+) + \Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{A}^-) - \Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{HA}) \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta G^{\circ}(\text{A}^-) = \Delta G_t^{\circ}(1) - \Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{H}^+) + \Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{HA}) \quad (7)$$

$\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$ stands for free energy change for the transfer of H^+ from the standard state in water to that in the solvent and may be taken as a measure of the basicity of the solvents with respect to that of water. The $\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$ values have been determined in our laboratory based on the experimental measurements of transfer of BH^+ ($\text{B} = 2,2'$ -bipyridyl) from water to mixed solvents with necessary physical parameters determined as well as taken from the literature⁹. The values of $\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{HA})$, $\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$, $\Delta G_t^{\circ}(1)$ and $\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{A}^-)$ have been recorded in Tables 5-8.

The solubility values (Tables 1-4) of the acids increase with the increase in the organic solvent content of the mixed solvents and show linear relationship when plotted against (i) mole-fraction and (ii) $1/\epsilon$ well upto ~ 70 wt% beyond which deviation occurs. It is observed that the solubility increases with decreasing dielectric constant of the medium. This increase might be due to the solute-solvent interactions, and the preferential solvation

TABLE 5—FREE ENERGY OF TRANSFER OF ANION $\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{A}^-)$ OF *p*-NITROBENZOIC ACID (in kJ) IN ME+H₂O AT 25°

ME wt%	$\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{HA})$	$\Delta G_t^{\circ}(1)$	$\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$	$\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{A}^-)$
10	-0.28	0.57	-1.33	1.62
20	-1.10	1.48	-2.47	2.85
30	-3.87	3.99	-3.48	3.60
40	-4.37	5.48	-4.19	5.30
50	-5.79	8.16	-5.69	8.06
60	-7.51	9.87	-7.06	9.42
70	-8.96	12.61	-9.14	12.79
80	-10.84	16.32	-11.63	17.11
90	-12.41	20.71	-13.23	21.53
100	-13.07	—	—	—

TABLE 6—FREE ENERGY OF TRANSFER OF ANION $\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{A}^-)$ OF *p*-NITROBENZOIC ACID (in kJ) IN DME+H₂O AT 25°

DME wt%	$\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{HA})$	$\Delta G_t^{\circ}(1)$	$\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$	$\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{A}^-)$
10	-0.53	1.20	-2.15	2.82
20	-1.29	2.17	-3.65	4.53
30	-3.95	4.85	-5.09	5.99
40	-6.11	6.50	-6.78	7.17
50	-6.74	8.62	-8.48	10.36
60	-10.63	11.58	-10.27	11.22
70	-12.10	13.92	-12.82	14.64
80	-13.79	18.32	-14.63	19.16
90	-14.14	23.22	-17.62	26.70
100	-14.39	—	—	—

TABLE 7—FREE ENERGY OF TRANSFER OF ANION $\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{A}^-)$ OF *p*-CHLOROBENZOIC ACID (in kJ) IN ME+H₂O AT 25°

ME wt%	$\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{HA})$	$\Delta G_t^{\circ}(1)$	$\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$	$\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{A}^-)$
10	-1.20	3.54	-1.33	3.67
20	-2.92	4.56	-2.47	4.11
30	-4.32	6.22	-3.48	4.86
40	-6.54	7.47	-4.19	5.12
50	-7.45	9.93	-5.69	8.17
60	-9.25	12.84	-7.06	10.65
70	-10.42	14.32	-9.14	13.04
80	-12.55	17.12	-11.63	16.20
90	-14.32	21.34	-13.23	20.25
100	-15.42	—	—	—

TABLE 8—FREE ENERGY OF TRANSFER OF ANION $\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{A}^-)$ OF *p*-CHLOROBENZOIC ACID (in kJ) IN DME+H₂O AT 25°

DME wt%	$\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{HA})$	$\Delta G_t^{\circ}(1)$	$\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{H}^+)$	$\Delta G_t^{\circ}(\text{A}^-)$
10	-1.56	4.45	-2.15	5.04
20	-3.28	6.50	-3.65	6.87
30	-5.41	7.42	-5.09	7.10
40	-8.00	9.53	-6.78	8.31
50	-10.17	11.58	-8.48	9.84
60	-11.83	13.92	-10.27	12.36
70	-14.36	16.89	-12.82	15.35
80	-16.00	22.54	-14.63	21.17
90	-16.53	26.42	-17.62	27.51
100	-17.76	—	—	—

of the solute molecules by the organic solvent at the higher percentages of the mixed solvents may cause this deviation. However, it is interesting to note that the solubility of the respective acid is greater in DME or DME+H₂O mixtures compared to that in ME or ME+H₂O mixtures, the values

being greater for *p*-nitrobenzoic acid than *p*-chlorobenzoic acid. The number of CH₂ groups relative to that of hydrophilic OH groups being greater in DME, a greater dispersion effect is expected in DME+H₂O and this may be largely responsible for the greater stability of the acids (more negative $\Delta G_t^\circ(\text{HA})$) in DME+H₂O compared to ME+H₂O as observed. Again, the difference in the behaviour of the solubilities of *p*-chloro- and *p*-nitro-benzoic acids in the solvent systems can be qualitatively explained on the basis of solute-solvent dipole interactions and the relative solvent basicities. The $\Delta G_t^\circ(\text{H}^+)$ values are found to be increasingly negative both in ME+H₂O and DME+H₂O indicating increased stabilisation of H⁺ in the mixed solvents. The $\Delta G_t^\circ(\text{H}^+)$ values indicate that the solvent mixtures become increasingly basic in character compared to water as the organic solvent component increases. The changes of the basicity of the solvent mixtures are reflected in the free energy of transfer of H⁺ ion and the solubility values of the acids. Presence of nitro group than the chloride group in the *para*-position of the benzene ring increases the polarity of that solute molecule to a large extent and the basicity is much greater in DME than in ME leading to an increase in solubility with increase in DME content of the solvent medium, the rate of increase being larger at higher percentage of the mixed solvents.

It can be seen from Tables that the pK_T values increase continuously with the increase in the percentage of organic solvent and show a linear relationship when plotted against $1/\epsilon$ at low percentages but deviations occur at higher percentages. It is also observed that the pK_T values are in the order, DME+H₂O > ME+H₂O mixtures, the values being greater for *p*-chlorobenzoic acid than *p*-nitrobenzoic acid, contrary to the solubility values of these acids in these solvent mixtures. The two solvents differ in their dielectric constant values and solvating capabilities. The dielectric constant of ME+H₂O is greater than DME+H₂O of similar mol % non-aqueous component, electrostatic interactions thus impart less positive contribution to $\Delta G_t^\circ(\text{A}^-)$ in ME+H₂O than in DME+H₂O resulting in more ionisation in the former than in the latter solvent system. However, the behaviour as reflected in the relative pK_T values of *p*-chloro-

and *p*-nitro-benzoic acids may be attributed to relative destabilisation of anions in these solvent systems and the results indicate their order to be Cl⁻ > NO₂⁻. The destabilisation of the anions are the results of decreased acidity of aquo-cosolvent mixture.

Tables 5-8 show the increasingly negative magnitudes of $\Delta G_t^\circ(\text{HA})$ with increase in mol% of ME or DME, the values being less negative in ME than DME. This indicates the stabilisation of these acids in these mixed solvents, primarily through dispersion forces¹⁰ and the basicity of the solvents are reflected on the ΔG_t° values, DME+H₂O is less acidic than ME+H₂O. The $\Delta G_t^\circ(\text{A}^-)$ values are predominantly positive and it is in agreement with the fact that ΔG_t° of anions are usually positive¹¹. The results indicate that the transfer of $\Delta G_t^\circ(\text{A}^-)$ is non-spontaneous from water to mixed solvents.

In conclusion, it may be said that the overall dissociation behaviour in these two solvent systems is dictated by specific solute-solvent interactions besides the effects of relative solvent basicities.

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References

1. A. K. MANDAL and S. C. LAHIRI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 894.
2. B. P. DEY, S. C. DUTTA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **25**, 1105.
3. A. N. CAMPBELL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 179.
4. "Hand Book of Chemistry", ed. N. A. LANGR, McGraw-Hill, New York, 1961, p. 457.
5. L. G. VAN UITERT and C. C. HAAS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 451.
6. H. SADEK, TH. F. TADROS and A. A. EL-HARAKANY, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1971, **16**, 389.
7. E. RENARD and J. C. JUSTICE, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1974, **3**, 8.
8. K. DAS, A. K. DAS, K. BOSE and K. K. KUNDU, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1978, **82**, 1242.
9. D. SENGUPTA, A. PAL and S. C. LAHIRI, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1983, 2685.
10. K. K. KUNDU, A. L. DEY and M. N. DAS, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1972, 2063.
11. C. F. WELLS, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1973, 984.